

The Impact Of Gadget Use On The Social-Emotional Abilities Of Children Aged 5-6 Years In Lumban Huayan Village, Sosa District, Padang Lawas Regency

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ABSTRACT

This study means to decide: (1) The effect of device use on youth, (2) The span of contraceptive use in youth, (3) The type of parental help when kids use contraceptives, (4) The effect of contraceptive use on youngsters' capacity to collaborate with companions and grown-ups, (5) The effect of device use on youngsters' feelings, (5) The effect of contraceptive use on kids' disciplinary mentalities. This kind of exploration is an unmistakable subjective examination. The subjects in this study were 11 kids aged 5-6 years who would use contraception more often than not. The exploration instruments utilized were perception and meetings. The outcomes showed that the utilization of devices in youngsters aged 5-6 years impressively affects kids' social-personal capacities.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, smartphones have become an important necessity for children and adults. The rapid progress of technology is very advanced and very significant. In the past, the technical conditions of villages were still far from those of big cities. In this era, the technological gap is starting to be bridged with various increasingly advanced information technologies. According to Pebriana (2017), he explains that today's gadgets are a real form of progress in science and technology, their development certainly has an impact on people's lifestyles, both in terms of ways of thinking as well as behavior. The use of gadgets in everyday life not only has an impact on adult human behavior, the use of gadgets has an impact on children, one of which is their social skills.

Early childhood is the most essential and fundamental period where children undergo rapid growth and development. Early childhood is a group of children aged 0 to 6 years, the stimulus distributed to children at this age plays a very important role in the child's subsequent development tasks. Providing appropriate stimulation to children can increase their growth and development and optimize their growth and development so that their growth and development are not hampered (Pratiwi, 2017).

Early childhood cannot be separated from socio-emotional development, socio-emotional development is a process where children learn to adapt to understand situations and emotions by socializing with people around them and listening, observing, and imitating what children see. According to Tirtayani (2014) Social and emotional are related to other developmental perspectives, both physical and mental. Skills complement the child's function in emotions which leads to memory, reasoning, and focus on the child in the psychological effects of pressure and impact character, interests, and other psychological effects.

Yudha et al (2005) explained that children's emotional behavior is greatly influenced by social reactions to children's emotional behavior. Children's social senses are developed from stimulus. These stimuli include auditory stimuli, tactile stimuli, social stimuli, and visual stimuli. From this view, it can be seen that children's social-emotional development is influenced by stimuli from the surrounding area, from the school environment, educators can encourage and provide stimuli so that children's social-emotional development can be optimal. Early childhood social emotions need to be developed because social emotions are children's first skills in socializing with their wider environment. In line with the views of Izzaty et al. (2008), many families and early childhood educators emphasize the importance of social-emotional development in early childhood and preschool children. Based on this view, children's socio-emotional development must be developed at the beginning of school, because before entering the school environment, children only know the family environment. Therefore, when children enter the school environment, they already have the basic social-emotional skills to adapt to a new environment.

From the exploration of Zaini & Soenarto (2019), the level of gadget use for kindergarten children aged 4 to 6 years is ninety-four percent. The impact of increasing the level of gadget usage among kindergarten-age children 4-6 years, includes: 1) gadgets and tablets as a means of introducing information and communication technology, 2) gadgets and tablets as educational media to increase children's understanding, and 3) gadgets and tablets as a means of entertainment so that children are not fussy.

According to Purwijayanti et al (2021), it was found that gadgets cause children's social interaction with the surrounding area to decrease, resulting in children tending to be lazy about moving and rarely engaging in motor activities because they are already using gadgets. Meanwhile, Rohmayani (2022), in his research, concluded that most children get emotional when they find out that the battery of the game/device/gadget they are playing with is dead or they are disturbed while playing, and children become emotionally. And most children also get emotional if they are not allowed to play. However, if children feel uncomfortable on the playground, most children will not leave the playground and most children will be able to play with their peers.

Based on initial observations by researchers in Lumban Huayan Village, Sosa District, Padang Lawas Regency on children aged 5-6 years who tend to use gadgets, researchers found that many children prefer to play with gadgets rather than play with friends their age. It can be seen that when friends their age play together in the field, children who often play with gadgets at home tend to be alone because they think the games played by their friends are less interesting and boring. The factor that children prefer to play with gadgets is also influenced by their parents' parenting style. The form of parenting that parents share with their children will have an impact on the child's social and emotional development. By field facts, researchers found that parents give gadgets to their fussy children so that the parents can quickly finish doing their homework and the children can be calm with their gadgets. If this continues to happen to a child, the child will become addicted to gadgets.

Based on the problems above, researchers wish to apply research on "The Impact Of Gadget Use On The Social Emotional Abilities Of Children Aged 5-6 Years In Lumban Huayan Village, Sosa District, Padang Lawas Regency".

LITERATURE REVIEW

Early Childhood Social-Emotional Skills

Suyadi (2010) explains that social-emotional development is a child's sensitivity to understanding the sentiments of other humans when socializing in human life. Based on this definition, it can be understood that social-emotional development cannot be separated. In other words, discussion of emotional development must be related to children's social

development. Likewise, discussions about social development must include emotions. Busthomi's (2012) view explains that social-emotional development plays a very essential task when determining the future of children's social interactions and behavior with other humans.

Various social-emotional development problems in early childhood can be seen when children meet and socialize with other people in everyday life. According to Wiyani's (2014) view, there are 5 social-emotional development problems, namely: fearfulness, anxiety, low self-esteem, shyness, and disobedience.

The characteristics of the social-emotional development of early childhood are those who prefer to work together with friends of their choosing, begin to follow and obey the rules in playing, and can control their emotions when implementing a game. And as for the standard level of achievement of social-emotional development in children aged 5-6 years is that children can socialize with peers and adults, show self-confidence, have an independent attitude, show normal emotions, are used to showing discipline and obey rules, can be responsible, protect oneself and the environment, willing to share, help and help friends.

The view of Novitasari & Khotimah (2016) states that one of the reasons and stimuli that can have a social and emotional impact on children is the child's habit of playing with gadgets. A child's introduction to gadgets usually starts with the wrong way of moving parents or family by focusing on games or videos on the gadget in the hope that the child will not be fussy or cry. Starting from this transfer, parents have indirectly introduced gadgets to their children and in the future, this can provoke children who are too curious about gadgets.

Gadget Use in Early Childhood

Trivena (2017) explains that gadgets are innovations based on the latest technology which introduces better displays and new displays that are more practical and useful. As it develops, the concept of devices also expands, treating devices as gadgets, and when new products appear, computers and portable equipment are also considered devices.

According to Starburger, a child should only be in front of a screen < 1 hour each day. This view is also supported by Sigman who stated that the ideal length of time for preschool-aged children to use gadgets is 30 minutes or 1 hour a day," Triastuti (in Ulfa, 2020). Gadgets are fine if they are used as necessary for positive things. and use by children must be under parental control, including restrictions, supervision, or assistance.

Saputri et al (2018) explained that gadgets have benefits, especially if they are used correctly, and families should be allowed to introduce gadgets to young children who are useful and must pay attention to the positive and negative effects of these devices. Devices have positive and negative influences. These influences are the positive impacts of use consist of:

1. Starting with imagination, (seeing a picture and then drawing it precisely, your imagination forges thinking

- power without being limited by reality).
2. Forging intelligence (children can get used to writing, numbers, and pictures to help forge the learning process).
 3. Increase self-confidence. (When children win a game they will be inspired to finish the game).
 4. Develop skills in reading, mathematics, and problem-solving. (Children will develop a basic curiosity about something, resulting in the child becoming aware of the need to learn on their own without needing to be forced).

The negative impacts of use consist of:

1. Decreased focus when studying (when studying the child becomes unfocused and remembers gadgets, for example, the child remembers gadget games as if he were a character in a game).
2. Laziness about writing and reading (caused by using gadgets, for example when children open a video on the YouTube application, children tend to just look at the picture without having to write what they are looking for).
3. Decreased social skills (children play less with friends in the surrounding area, and don't pay attention to the circumstances around them).
4. Addiction, (the child will have difficulty and will become dependent on gadgets because it has become necessary for him).
5. It can cause health diseases (obviously it can cause health diseases due to exposure to radiation in gadgets, and can also damage children's eye health).
6. The cognitive development of early childhood is hampered, (cognitive and psychological processes related to how individuals analyze, focus, observe, imagine, estimate, assess, and think about their environment will be hampered).
7. Inhibits language skills (children who are used to using gadgets will tend to be quiet, often imitate the language they hear, close themselves off, and are reluctant to communicate with friends and their environment).
8. Can have an impact on the behavior of young children, (for example, children playing games that have elements of violence which will have an impact on behavior patterns and character that can lead to acts of violence against friends).

METHODOLOGY

The type of research used in this research is descriptive qualitative research with a qualitative approach because this research aims to describe, explain, and analyze a phenomenon that occurs. This descriptive qualitative research focuses more on field observations rather than using statistical or quantification methods. This research will be implemented in Lumban Huayan Village, Sosa District, Padang Lawas Regency. The research location is the desired research place that can provide the information that researchers need. The research period

was carried out from August to October 2023.

The subjects in the exploration were 11 children aged 5-6 years who tended to use gadgets at home and with their parents in Lumban Huayan Village, Sosa District, Padang Lawas Regency. The object of exploration is the impact of gadget use on the social-emotional development of children aged 5-6 years in Lumban Huayan Village, Sosa District, Padang Lawas Regency.

Research procedures and designs are the processes and stages applied in research. This research was carried out in 3 procedural stages as follows: pre-field stage, field activity stage, and intensive analysis stage.

In qualitative research, the research instrument and tool is the researcher himself. Therefore, the researcher as an instrument must also be "validated" to what extent the researcher is prepared to implement the research that will next enter the field. The data collection techniques in this research consist of observation and interviews.

The exploration data analysis technique uses qualitative analysis techniques which have 3 stages, namely according to Miles & Huberman (Rangkuti, 2014) as follows: data reduction, data presentation, and conclusions.

RESEARCH RESULTS

This research was applied to children aged 5-6 years in Lumban Huayan Village who tend to use gadgets. In line with the research focus regarding the use of gadgets in early childhood, the duration of gadget use in early childhood, the form of parental assistance when children use gadgets, the impact of using gadgets on children's social skills with peers and adults, the impact of using gadgets on children's emotions, and The impact of gadget use on children's disciplinary attitudes.

Gadgets can be used by every human being, even children. Likewise, children aged 5-6 years in Lumban Huayan Village, tend to use gadgets every day.

1. Social-Emotional Skills

- a. **Interaction with Peers:** Children are involved in interactions with their peers when using gadgets together. They seem to be actively socializing with their friends, talking and sharing experiences while playing with gadgets. However, it should be noted that there are moments when children focus more on activities on gadgets than socializing with their friends. This

explains the importance of maintaining a balance between social interaction and gadget use.

- b. Emotional Response: In general, children respond well when their gadgets must be turned off or their time to play ends. However, they sometimes show signs of frustration or sadness when they have to stop playing. Adult humans need to help them manage this sentiment and provide an understanding of the importance of rules and limits in using gadgets.
- c. Nonverbal Communication: Children tend to be isolated when using gadgets, especially when the activities on the gadget are very interesting. They focus more on the gadget screen and communicate less with the surrounding area. Even so, they still show the right facial expressions for the activities they do on their gadgets.

2. Aggressive Behavior

Some children, for example, Zidan Lubis and Alzam Pasaribu, sometimes display aggressive behavior, especially when they have to share gadgets with their friends. They can be emotional or difficult to share. Apart from that, there is a tendency for them to imitate the aggressive behavior seen in the media content they watch on their gadgets. This emphasizes the importance of adult human supervision in deciding appropriate gadget content and provides an understanding of healthy social behavior.

3. Attention and Task Skills

Children's use of gadgets sometimes causes them to be less focused on tasks or other activities that do not involve gadgets. They often have difficulty shifting attention from gadgets to other activities. In the long term, this can impact their skills to complete tasks and other activities.

4. Transformation in Behavior

There has been a transformation in the behavior of the four children since they started using gadgets more intensively. They become more independent in carrying out daily activities and are responsive to the rules and limits set. However, there is also an increase in aggressive behavior in some contexts. In other words, the impact of gadget use on children is not only positive but can also have negative sides that need to be taken into account.

Duration of gadget use in early childhood in Lumban Huayan Village

1. Shaqil Pasaribu: Shaqil uses gadgets for 1-2 hours a day. This relatively short duration of use seems to help him maintain his level of concentration and interaction with his friends.
2. Rafif Daulyay: Rafif uses gadgets for 1-3 hours a day. The fairly

short duration of use seems to give him enough time to continue socializing with friends and completing daily tasks well. However, Rafif tends to be less involved in socializing with his peers.

3. Muhammad Al-Zikri: Zikri uses gadgets for 1-2 hours a day. The shorter duration of use means that Zikri does not focus too much, especially on concentration levels and aggressive behavior. He sometimes finds it difficult to share gadgets and shows signs of frustration when he has to stop playing.
4. Muhammad Refli: Refli uses gadgets for 1-2 hours a day, which is a fairly low usage duration. The impact begins to become more visible with increased aggressive behavior and difficulty in shifting attention from gadgets to other activities.
5. Imam Hanafi: Imam uses gadgets for 1-2 hours a day, Imam explains signs of aggressive behavior and difficulty in shifting attention from gadgets.
6. Mira Nasution: Mira uses gadgets for 1 hour a day. He generally responds well to mandatory stops. Apart from that, he explained his skills in socializing with his friends when using gadgets together.
7. Nurul Hasibuan: Nurul uses gadgets for 2-3 hours a day. This relatively long duration of use seems to have resulted in Nurul being lazy about socializing with his friends.
8. Rahmadani: Rahmadani uses gadgets for 2-3 hours a day. Even though he has been around longer than Nurul, he still maintains the skills to socialize with his friends and responds well when he has to stop playing. However, sometimes, there are moments when he focuses more on gadgets than his friends.
9. Rahmad Harahap: Rahmad uses gadgets for 30 minutes to 1 hour a day, generally responding well when required to stop playing, although there are some signs of frustration. Apart from that, he explained his skills in socializing with his friends when using gadgets together.
10. Zidan Lubis: Zidan uses gadgets for 2-3 hours a day, this longer duration of use is starting to impact his behavior and makes it difficult for him to shift his attention from the gadget.
11. Alzam Pasaribu: Alzam uses gadgets for 1-2 hours a day. The relatively short duration of use seemed to help him maintain his concentration on tasks and social interactions.

A form of parental assistance when children use gadgets in Lumban Huayan Village

1. Shaqil Pasaribu: Shaqil's parents are actively involved in using his gadgets. They limit the duration of use and ensure that the content is age-appropriate.
2. Rafif Daulay: Rafif's parents provide good support. They help him decide on educational content and are always there to

answer any questions that may arise.

3. Muhammad Al-Zikri: Zikri's parents also provide active assistance. They are always around him and make sure he uses his gadgets wisely.
4. Muhammad Refli: Refli's parents provide a little assistance in using gadgets. This can contribute to aggressive behavior and difficulty in controlling gadget use.
5. Imam Hanafi: Hanafi's parents are also actively involved in mentoring him. They monitor gadget usage time and ensure that Nadia's experience remains positive.
6. Mira Nasution: Mira's parents provide good support. They help him decide on educational content and are always there to answer any questions that may arise.
7. Nurul Hasibuan: Nurul Hasibuan's parents are actively involved in assisting him when he uses gadgets. They often play together with Nurul and guide her in choosing the right content.
8. Rahmad Harahap: Rahmad's parents are also actively involved in using his gadgets. They are always around and ensure that he safely uses gadgets and limits his time.
9. Rahmadani: Rahmadani's parents provide a little assistance in using gadgets. This seems to hurt aggressive behavior and difficulty in controlling gadget use.
10. Zidan Lubis: Zidan's parents provide a little assistance when he uses gadgets. They are more likely to give him freedom in terms of content selection. The impact is that Zidan tends to have difficulty controlling the duration of his gadget usage.
11. Alzam Pasaribu: Alzam's parents are also less involved in using his gadgets. They gave him freedom in deciding the content, which contributed to his aggressive behavior.

The impact of gadget use on children's social skills with peers and adults in LumbanHuayan Village

1. Interaction with Peers
 - a. The results of the exploration show that most children aged 5-6 years show a high level of interaction with their friends when using gadgets together. Some children, for example, Imam Hanafi, Mira Nasution, and Zidan Lubis seemed very active in talking, laughing, and sharing experiences with their friends while playing with gadgets. They can establish positive social interactions while playing with gadgets, demonstrating good social-emotional skills in this situation.
 - b. Even though most children socialize with their peers, there are moments when their focus is more focused on activities on their gadgets, indicating that their interactions are not always

optimal. This could indicate that gadget use can have an impact on the intensity of children's social interactions, even if they socialize while using gadgets.

2. Interaction with Adult Humans
 - a. Although the data provided does not specifically discuss the impact of gadget use on children's interactions with adults, we can assume that there are similar implications. Children may spend more time with gadgets, reducing the time they spend socializing with adults, especially parents and caregivers.
 - b. Long-term use of gadgets by children can reduce their direct interaction with adult humans which is very important for their development. It can result in a decline in family communication, lost opportunities to learn from adults and other impacts on child-adult interactions.
3. Transformation in Behavior
 - a. Research also shows that there has been a transformation in children's behavior since they started using gadgets more intensively. Although some of this includes increased independence and responsiveness to rules and limits, there is also an increase in aggressive behavior in some contexts.
 - b. Aggressive behavior can include disobedience in adult humans, especially when having to stop using gadgets, as well as aggressive behavior in situations of sharing gadgets with friends. This shows that the use of gadgets can have a complex impact on children's social-emotional behavior, including interactions with adults.

The impact of gadget use on children's emotions in Lumban Huayan Village

1. Variations in Emotional Responses: Research findings show that there are variations in children's emotional responses when asked to stop using gadgets. Some children respond well without signs of excessive frustration, while others may feel disappointed or emotional. This indicates that the use of gadgets impacts children's emotions differently.
2. Healthy Emotional Response: The majority of children show a healthy emotional response when they have to stop using gadgets. This includes their understanding of the rules and boundaries imposed by parents. Children, for example, Imam Hanafi, Mira Nasution, and Zidan Lubis responded well, showing a good understanding of limiting the time they use gadgets.
3. Difficulty in Stopping: Some children may find it difficult to stop using gadgets suddenly. This can lead to emotional reactions such as disappointment or anxiety. The increase in emotional intensity when you have to stop using gadgets

shows that there is dependence and emotional attachment to this technology.

4. Emotional Transformation Over Time: In the context of behavioral transformation, research also shows that there has been a transformation in children's behavior and emotions since they started using gadgets more intensively. This includes increased independence and understanding of rules but also increased aggressive behavior in some cases. This illustrates that gadget use can have a complex impact on children's emotions over time.
5. Behavior Related to Using Gadgets: Emotional responses can also be related to behavior related to using gadgets. When children are faced with restrictions on usage time or are asked to stop using gadgets, their emotional reactions can impact their behavior. Most of the children showed cooperative behavior, but some showed aggressive behavior in several situations, for example, Rahmad Harahap, Alzam Pasaribu, and Radinka Hamda.

The impact of gadget use on children's disciplinary attitudes in Lumban Huayan Village

1. Variations in Gadget Usage Patterns: Data shows that children aged 5 years show variations in their gadget usage patterns. Some children have strict time rules, while others have more flexibility in using gadgets. This variation reflects differences in the level of discipline of children in following the rules and limits imposed by parents.
2. Clear Time Rules: One of the findings is that clear time rules can help increase children's level of discipline in following these rules. Children who have strict time rules, for example, Rahmat, tend to be more disciplined in following these rules. This shows that strict time rules can help control gadget use and provide a consistent time frame for children.
3. Active supervision by parents: In managing gadget use, active supervision by parents also plays an important role in forming children's disciplinary attitudes. Parents who closely monitor and supervise their children's gadget activities can encourage them to follow the rules and avoid excessive gadget use.
4. Regular Evaluation: Findings also include the importance of regular evaluation of the impact of gadget use. By implementing regular evaluations, parents can monitor their children's behavior and level of discipline. If a child displays deficiencies in discipline, adjustments to rules and limits can be implemented to ensure healthier gadget use.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of interviews and observations carried out in LumbanHuayan Village on 11 children aged 5-6 years and 11 parents, it was found that impact of gadget use in early childhood is:

1. **Social-Emotional Skills:** Research results show that young children tend to socialize with their peers when using gadgets. This is a positive sign, showing that the use of gadgets can facilitate social interaction. However, it is also important to remember that there needs to be a balance between interaction with gadgets and interaction with friends directly.
2. **Aggressive Behavior:** Some children show signs of aggressive behavior, especially related to using gadgets and sharing with their friends. Explaining that the use of gadgets can have an impact on children's social behavior. This requires appropriate monitoring and intervention from adult humans.

Duration of Gadget Use in Early Childhood:

1. **Wise Time Limits:** The duration of gadget use in early childhood varies greatly. However, the findings show that children with strict time limits tend to be better at managing gadget use and maintaining a better level of discipline.
2. **Adult Supervision:** Adult supervision, especially by parents, has proven to be effective when regulating the duration of gadget use. Parents who actively monitor their children's gadget activities can help them comply with the rules set.
3. **The Importance of Outdoor Activities:** The findings show that balancing gadget use with outdoor activities is very important. Children who engage in physical activity and social interactions outdoors tend to have more balanced lives.

Forms of Parental Assistance When Children Use Gadgets:

1. **Active Assistance:** Parents who are actively involved in their children's gadget use can provide direction, ensure appropriate content selection, and help limit the duration of gadget use.
2. **Variations in Assistance:** There are variations in parental assistance, and the impact can be seen in the child's level of discipline. Parents who provide stronger support tend to help children develop better discipline in using gadgets.

The Impact of Using Gadgets on Children's Socialization Skills with Peers and Adults

1. **Interaction with Peers:** Most children show a high level of interaction with peers when using gadgets. This is a positive sign that gadget use does not have to reduce their social interactions, but rather attention needs to be paid to maintaining balance.
2. **Interaction with Adult Humans:** Although not specifically

researched, it can be assumed that excessive use of gadgets can reduce children's interactions with adult humans. It is important to ensure that children remain involved in direct interactions with their parents and caregivers.

Impact of Using Gadgets on Children's Emotions

1. Variations in Emotional Responses: There are variations in children's emotional responses when they have to stop using gadgets. A healthy emotional response is a sign of understanding the rules, while a difficult or negative emotional response indicates the possibility of dependency or other negative impacts.
2. Behavior related to gadget use: Emotional responses can also impact behavior related to gadget use. Children who find it difficult to stop using gadgets can display aggressive or frustrated behavior.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

1. Gadget use in early childhood has a complex impact on their social- emotional skills. While children can socialize with their peers when using gadgets, there needs to be a balance between social interaction and gadget use. Some children described aggressive behavior related to gadget use, which emphasizes the importance of selecting appropriate content and adult supervision.
2. The duration of gadget use varies, but the findings show that clear time limits and active parental supervision contribute to better discipline in managing gadget use.
3. Parental support when children use gadgets plays a key role in shaping children's experiences. Actively involved parents can help children decide on appropriate content, obey rules, and maintain good disciplinary attitudes.
4. The use of gadgets can also have an impact on children's interactions with peers and adults. To ensure balanced social development, it is important to protect direct interactions with peers and adult humans.
5. The impact of gadget use on children's emotions can vary. Healthy emotional responses reflect an understanding of rules, while difficult emotional responses indicate dependency or other negative impacts. This impact can also have an impact on behavior related to gadget use.
6. The use of gadgets on children's disciplinary attitudes. Children's discipline in using gadgets often depends on

parental control. Parents who do not properly regulate their children's use of gadgets cause children to lose their discipline in managing their time because they play too many games and watch videos.

Recommendations

Based on the results from previously formulated conclusions, the author provides input in the form of suggestions, as follows:

1. For Parents

Parents should be more selective to optimize the use of gadgets in early childhood. Parents and caregivers need to continue to monitor, organize, and provide wise assistance. Involves choosing the right content, setting the duration of gadget use, and ensuring that children remain involved in healthy social interactions. With the right approach, the positive impact of gadget use on early childhood development can be increased, while the negative impact can be minimized.

2. For Researchers

It is hoped that this research will provide a reference for subsequent research. Especially for researchers who will research the impact of gadget use on children's social-emotional skills.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

For advanced research, we hope to be able to see or analyze the use of gadgets not only for social-emotional abilities but also from other aspects.

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